

CORRESPONDENCE OF LEGAL TERMS TO THE STANDARDS OF LITERARY LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7539636>

Annotation. This article is devoted to the problems of terms and its specific features of legal terms. It also discusses peculiarities of legal terms and usage of them in different texts.

Keywords: terms, terminology, words, lexical features.

Legal terms form the main layer of the lexicon of the legal language. Vocabulary units and terms used in the legislation, which have been formed over the years and are being improved with the honor of independence, are distinguished by the color of formality. Such a rich vocabulary is a witness of our great national value and the existence of Uzbek statehood and rights.

The quality of discoveries related to legal branches, the priority of laws also depends on the skillful use of language tools, in particular terms, which are directly related to Oman. In the present process, in which practical steps are being taken towards the further improvement of the legal democratic society, while the reforms related to the provision of human rights and freedoms, the achievement of the primacy of laws, and the introduction of a consistent and perfect system of state administration are underway, the language and style of laws, legal terminology, and various terminological and orthographical aspects of jurisprudence branches , creating a "new generation" of explanatory, encyclopedic dictionaries and manuals is one of the most urgent issues.

Due to the development of our independent statehood, the adoption of various laws related to human rights, in turn, causes the emergence of thousands of new terms related to law, because the birth of any concept or phenomenon in social life causes the enrichment of terms as a reflection of it. However, when emerging legal concepts find their reflection in the language as words or terms, they must be expressed and formed based on the laws of the national language. Let's say, do the legal terms that are being chosen and entering into daily communication express the exact names of events and signs and concepts, do the Uzbek alternatives of the terms borrowed from other languages comply with the standards of the literary language or not? It will be appropriate if these issues find their exact solution in cooperation between lawyers and philologists. It is a necessity for law makers to study the knowledge of the branches of statehood, legislation and jurisprudence on the basis of the state language, in an integral

connection with the specific laws, methodology and terminology of this language.

About 400 laws have been adopted since the independence of our republic. This is definitely a positive thing. Because every adopted law serves human well-being and development of society. Although most of these laws have been prepared in accordance with the standards of the literary language, the articles of some of our laws still require editing and are linguistically incomplete.

The language of the law is a component of the literary language, and it is a form of language that requires its own lexical, terminological, grammatical, and methodological standards.

In the text of the law, the incorrect use of a single word or term, or even a single punctuation mark, can cause stylistic errors and ambiguities. That is why every law that is approved by the parliament, every article of it must be drafted in accordance with the standards of literary language. Because in the essence of the laws and each of their articles lies the human destiny and factor¹.

The use of several terms for the same concept in various legal sources (laws, decrees, textbooks, various training manuals, pamphlets, legal journals, terminological dictionaries, etc.) is still not justified. For example: administration-authority, suspect-suspect, instruction-indication, joint-stock company-joint-stock company, criminal case-criminal case, parties-parties, upper house-senate, lower house-legislature, etc. Many more such examples can be cited. Such situations occur as a result of our jurists' lack of understanding of the requirements for the term and the norms of the literary language. However, terms should be official words that have their own passports, approved by state authorities, and only then should they be allowed to enter social life. There are universally recognized rules about the essence of the term in world linguistics. One of them is: The term performs a nominative function. The meaning of the term must be equal to the concept. Because in a terminological system, the term is single-meaning, that is, monosemantic, so its meaning is equal to the concept. That is, terms are special formal words that express the same meaning.

To be more precise, there should be as many terms as there are legal concepts in the language. No synonyms or doublets are allowed in one terminological system. Therefore, regulation and uniformity of legal terms is one of the urgent issues of today. For this purpose, the compilation of orthographic and explanatory dictionaries of legal terms or the publication of explanatory,

¹ Воинова М.Г. Культура речи юриста. - Т.: ТДЮИ, 2003.

bilingual, encyclopedic dictionaries on each branch of jurisprudence will give the intended result.

In some articles of the law, there are mistakes and misunderstandings in the application and interpretation of simple terms. For example, "Defamation, i.e., knowingly spreading falsehoods that embarrass another person..." is explained in Article 40 of the Code of Administrative Responsibility. The word "shame" in the article is stylistically incorrect. It seems that the creator of the law did not even think of using the existing "explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language" when compiling this text. We read the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" in our hands. The word slander has a very beautiful definition: an unfounded claim, slander made with the purpose of accusing or defaming someone (O'TIL, Volume II, p. 241)

Although there are about 3,000 languages on earth, there is no language that consists of only one language. Words from one or another language are acquired due to communication and interaction in each language. As a result, there is an acquired layer in the language. Also, in the lexicon of the Uzbek language, there is a layer of words borrowed from other languages (of course, unrelated languages) in addition to its own layer. However, some words and terms do not match the standards and criteria of the Uzbek literary language due to the fact that they were blindly copied from the Russian language and other European languages through it. As a result, unusual legal terms appear. For example, the term Criminal Code is wrongly translated from Russian (Ugolovnyy kodeks). In fact, it is appropriate to use this term in accordance with the norms of the Uzbek literary language in the form of "Collection of Laws on Crime and Punishment" or "Crime and Punishment Code". The term "Criminal Code", derived from the Russian language, refers to the concept of codes (set of laws) related to crime. Or the term "Criminal Law" is also a stylistic nonsense. If you pay attention to the essence, the meaning of the right given to the crime will be understood. From the point of view of the Uzbek language, it is appropriate to call this title "Law of Crime and Punishment" or "Basics of Crime and Punishment". Or the translation of the Russian term "deputatskoe rassledovanie" as "deputy inspection" does not correspond to the norms of the literary language. As you know, the Russian word for audit is revision.

Translating this term as a deputy's inspection corresponds to the standards of the Uzbek literary language and means complete thought.

It is not difficult to understand that a funny situation has arisen especially because the name of the subject "Criminal executive law" was wrongly

translated into Uzbek. That is, if we pay attention to the meaning of this term, it means the right to commit crimes. In fact, according to the standards of the Uzbek literary language, it is appropriate to use this term in the form of "The right to execute punishment" or "Execution of punishment". Once upon a time, terms of such a form were mistranslated from the Russian language and introduced into the science. Over time, such terms have become commonplace. This in itself indicates that the expert in the field of law has not mastered the laws of the language well. This situation is the result of illiteracy. According to the sages, "Ignorance of the rules of the language is the supreme punishment of fate"².

Therefore, in accordance with the laws of the language, from which language words are adopted into the Uzbek language, it is necessary to first look for the alternative of such words in the Uzbek language itself. If the Uzbek equivalent of the words learned from other languages cannot be found, it is intended to translate not literally, but spiritually.

An important feature of legal terms is their close connection. Therefore, their development is determined by the level of development of legal theory and legal regulation in general. In the following years, with the expansion of domestic statehood, democratization of society and the development of legal science, the rule of law, social state, human rights and other similar terms were widely spread in legal documents. Naturally, strengthening their constitutional position requires certain scientific theoretical justification and the development of the science of law in general. After all, it is necessary to consider legal terms not only as a technical tool, but also as the most important scientific legal category.

Thus, legal terminology and the concepts defined by it are closely related to each other. Sometimes there are fundamental differences between them. Legal terminology is considered the most important tool of legal technique, its concept as a means of theoretically describing the law scientifically.

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² Воинова М.Г. Культура речи юриста. - Т.: ТДЮИ, 2003.

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